
MIRZO ULUGBEK INVALUABLE CONTRIBUTION TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE AS AN ENCYCLOPEDIST.

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Annotation

In this article, the invaluable contribution of Mirzo Ulugbek to the development of science as an encyclopedist, how wise and consistent Ulugbek was in his state policy, patronage of scientists, religious leaders, trade and crafts do not try to encourage the people, information about the opposition forces against him is given.

Keywords

science, politics, religion, trade, craftsman, khiroj, ushr, stamp, zakat, smoke tax, garden tax, capricorn, medicine, mirobona, begor.

INTRODUCTION.

The scientific courage of the great Amir Temur's grandson, Benazir Allama Mirzo Ulugbek, in the conditions of the Middle Ages, does not fail to amaze even today's scientists. Fate entrusted this great man with enormous and difficult tasks. He was given the very responsible task of becoming the successor of the kingdom created by the great general Amir Temur. Mirza Ulugbek, as a wise ruler of Movarounnahr region for almost forty years, showed great courage and perseverance in the pursuit of the people's eternal dream - peace, harmony, development of science and culture. This extraordinary allama created a perfect astronomical chart that included the movements of thousands of stars. Today's most modern devices confirm how accurate and correct the scientific data mentioned in this table are. Ulugbek's life and scientific activity are one of the cornerstones of our nation's spirituality, and it shows how much importance was attached to the development of fundamental sciences in our country long ago. The fact that Ulugbek's astronomical table called "Zizhi jadidi Ko'ragoniy" was translated into Latin in the Middle Ages and became widespread among European scientists is a clear proof of our opinion. While talking about this, I involuntarily

remember a conversation I had in Paris in 1996 with Mr. Federico Mayor, the Secretary General of UNESCO at that time. At that time, Mr. Mayor praised Ulugbek's scientific legacy and said that his calculations on the movement of stars were found to differ by only a few minutes when checked by a computer today. Then I answered him, no, Mr. Federico Mayor, Ulugbek may not have made a mistake, but the computers may have made a mistake. Although this was said as a friendly compliment, I think there is a deep truth behind it [1-5].

MAIN PART.

Although Amir Temur established a powerful kingdom, expanded its territories to the east-west, north-south, and made his era famous in the world by raising it from economic, cultural and spiritual aspects, but after his death, the country went into decline. The main reason for this is that the countries and territories included in Amir Temurtasarrufi were so diverse and spread over long distances that it was difficult to manage them from a single center for a long time. Moreover, it was natural that sooner or later the existing various opposition forces would work for their territorial independence. One of the important reasons that led to the weakening and disintegration of the Sahibqiran kingdom is the fruitless war and conflicts between a large number of Timurid princes, which began to fight for the throne and lasted for several years. Because, after the death of Amir Temur, his numerous successors did not listen to his wise wills and teachings, and began to fight for central power. Amir Temur left for the Chinese campaign and died of illness in O'tror on February 18, 1405. 2 of his 4 sons (Mironshah and Shahrukh Mirzolar) and 19 grandchildren, 15 great-grandchildren, as well as daughters - Agha Begim, Sultan Bakht Begim and Agha Begim's son Sultan Husayn Mirzolar were left. According to Amir Temur's will, his grandson Pirmuhammad (son of Jahangir Mirza) who was in charge of Kabul, Kandahar and North Indian lands should take his place. However, Prince Halil Sultan (son of Mironshah) arbitrarily occupied Samarkand and declared himself as the ruler, naturally, it led to the agitation of other princes and the division of the kingdom. As a result, a large part of the western regions soon became independent. On the Azerbaijani side, the movement of disobedience and resistance against Timur's kingdom by the Turkmen White and Black Rabbit dynasties intensified. Amir Khudaidad and Sheikh Nuriddin rose up in different regions of Movarounnahr [6-10]. Only the determined and courageous Shahrukh Mirza will put an end to these bloody disputes and wars and will gain the reins of power in Khurasan and Movarounnahr. In 1409, he resolved the situation in Movarounnahr in his favor and handed it over to his eldest son Ulugbek. His grandfather, Amir Temur, treated him with great

affection and brought him up from an early age. Ulug'bek (he was fondly called by this name in the family of Sahibgiron) possessed great innate talent and intelligence, in addition to mastering state administration, he mastered religious and worldly knowledge at a mature level. The reign of Mirzo Ulugbek (1409-1449) is a special period in the traditional development of the Timurid kingdom and the advancement of important social changes. After all, thanks to the great efforts of the wise ruler and the rightly oriented policy, the country's inviolability, peace and tranquility were relatively ensured. This had a significant positive impact on its economic, cultural and spiritual development. According to the unanimous opinion of the historians of that time, Ulugbek tried to keep the management system and all the procedures of his grandfather's time in full. He also followed it in tax and financial policy. True, Ulug'bek was not interested in battles like Amir Temur. He didn't have too much incentive in this field. He embarked on military campaigns only when necessary. For this reason, issues related to the development of the country, peace, well-being of the country, and the development of science occupy the main place in his work. Trade, crafts and agriculture in the country will continue to develop as before. Many artificial irrigation facilities will be built. The country actively participates in international caravan trade through the Great Silk Road [11-15]. In Samarkand, Bukhara, Shakhrisabz, Shosh and other cities, many luxurious madrasas, mosques, mausoleums, and caravanserais are built. The observatory, a unique architectural structure built under his direct leadership, embodied the latest achievements of the science and technology of that time.

The monetary reform carried out by Ulugbek in 1428 was also an important event in the establishment of trade and money circulation and financial policy in the country. The coins of new weight, issued by Ulugbek, played a special role in revitalizing economic life and developing trade with their value and value. During his time, the order of giving special privileges to representatives of the upper class, military commanders, and high priests prevailed, as before. In addition, large-scale waqf lands were also at the disposal of religious institutions, which are considered the great spiritual support of the state.

Among the various taxes paid by the population during the Timurid period, khiroj (land tax) stood out. At least one-third of the crops grown by the peasants were paid in taxes. In addition, tithe (one-tenth of the income), tamga (a tax on trade and artisans), zakat, tobacco tax, garden tax, ulaq (for civil servants), drug (military for shepherds), mirobona (for water suppliers), yasak (for livestock), begor (production at the expense of the state: for the construction of palaces, ditches, canals) and other taxes and duties were introduced [16-20].

No matter how much Ulugbek tried to conduct intelligent and consistent policies in his state policy, to patronize scientists, religious leaders, and encourage trade and crafts people, there were many opposing forces against him. When Ulugbek saw measures to limit the abuses of large landowners against ordinary citizens, they opposed the "scientist on the throne". Pro-ignorant elements among the clerics campaigned that Ulugbek was an "infidel ruler" who harmed the Islamic religion. In this way, those who love ignorance opposed science, and those who put their interests above the interests of the people opposed development. Ulugbek could not completely eliminate the internal conflicts between different socio-political groups in the country, the opposition of bigoted and reactionary forces. By the end of the 40s of the 15th century, the state of Movarounnahr was subject to instability and deep social upheavals. The fact that the country's army was not in a fighting condition and scattered in different places opened a wide way for the Dashti Kipchak settlers to often invade these lands and plunder the country. In particular, in connection with the death of Shahrukh Mirza in 1447, Ulugbek marched to Khurasan claiming his father's throne, clashed with his nephew Aloudovla and other heirs, and in his absence, Abulkhair Khan was the head of Dashti.

The looting of the lands of Movorounnahr by the Kipchaks, and finally, due to the instigation of the black forces, the conflict that began with his son Abdullatif turned into a big battle, in which Ulugbek was defeated - these are not only his tragic death did not end with, but at the same time led to the deepening of the crisis of the Timurid dynasty. The Ulugbek Academy was disbanded, the books in the library were burned, the scientists were forced to leave. The development of science. We should be proud of how much science has flourished in this golden age and its invaluable contribution to the development of world science [21-25].

Works by Mirzo Ulugbek:

"Zizhi Koragony". The position and position of 1018 stars are defined in this work. the coordinates of 683 geographical places in the world are determined in relation to the latitude of Samarkand. "History of Four Nations"

Works of Rumi in Qaziza:

"Risola fil khash" ("A treatise on accounting")

"Sharhi Mulahas fil-hayyat" ("Commentary on the basics of astronomy")

"Risolatul Jayb" ("Treatise on Sinus")

Commentary on Taftazani's "Miftahul-ulum" ("The Key of Knowledge").

Works of Ghiyasiddin Jamshid:

"Suslam us-samo" ("Ladder of Heaven")

"Risalat ul-atwar wal-jayb" ("Treatise on Vatars and Sinus")

Examples of the work of scientists of the Ulugbek Academy

Works of Ali Kushchi: "Risola dar ilmi calc" "Risolai qusur" "Risola dar handasa" "Risola dar falakiyot" "Risola dar ilmi hayyat" "Risolai mantiq"

Another important achievement of this period is the creation of great researches in the field of social sciences, in particular, historiography. The initiative and leadership of the Timurid rulers was incomparable in the emergence of these good deeds. In particular, there is no doubt that Amir Temur's "Tuzuklar", Mirzo Ulugbek's "History of Four Nations", Babur Mirzo's "Boburnoma" had a special influence on the development of social sciences.

Among the scholars who left a significant mark during the Timurid era are "Zafarnama" by Nizamiddin Shami and Sharafiddin Yazdi, "Zubdat at-tawarikh" by Hafizu Abru, "Matla ul-sa'dain" by Abdurazzaq Samarkandi and "Majma' ul-bahrayn" ("The Rising of the Two Blessed Stars"). 'rni and the confluence of two Azim rivers"), Ibn Arabshah's "History of Amir Temur", Mirkhand's seven-volume "Rawzat ul-Safa" ("Garden of Purity"), Khondamir's "Makorimul Akhlaq" ("Good Virtues"), " The works of Habibus siyar fi akhboru afodul bashar" ("Messages and close-to-heart stories from people of humanity") express the high level of historiography of that time [26-29].

CONCLUSION

To sum up, the most important thing is that this era brought a great figure like Amir Temur to the field of history. Movarounnahr and Khurasan lands underwent great changes due to the unparalleled efforts and creative activities of this breed of sharif and his descendants. Our motherland, completely freed from the invasion and oppression of the Mongols for a century and a half, rose to the level of a powerful kingdom. At the same time, it rose from the socio-economic, cultural and spiritual aspects and spread its influence to the world. High examples of material and spiritual culture created by our great ancestors, precious jewels, have been admiring the people of the world for centuries and have been cherished by grateful generations.

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